

Complete integers

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May-June 2022

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Introduction

In this work we will define a superset of integers (the complete integers, \mathbb{Z}_C), which contains the dual of integers along parity (e.g. the odd zero, the even one, ...). Then we will see how they form a ring and how they can be used as exponents for real numbers powers, in order to write functions which have a discontinuity in zero (the function itself or one of its derivatives), as for example $|x|$ and $\text{sgn}(x)$.

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Created with Agda and R bookdown.

The source files can be found at <https://gitlab.com/DPDmancul/complete-integers-agda>.

Chapter 1

Complete integer numbers

In this chapter we will define the ring of complete integers (\mathbb{Z}_C) and we will see that it is a superset of \mathbb{Z} . Then we will call the remaining dis-integers (\mathbb{Z}_D), which are the dual of integers (\mathbb{Z}) along parity (e.g. in \mathbb{Z} the unit is odd, in \mathbb{Z}_D the unit is even).

Definition 1.1 (Complete integers). Let's define the set of the complete integer numbers as

$$\mathbb{Z}_C := \mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{F}_2$$

We will call the first component *value*, and the second *parity*.

```
record  $\mathbb{Z}_C$  : Set where
  constructor [_,_]
  field
    val :  $\mathbb{Z}$ 
    par :  $\mathbb{F}_2$ 
```

Definition 1.2 (Ring of complete integers). Let's define \mathbb{Z}_C as a commutative ring with unit:

Given $[a, b], [c, d] \in \mathbb{Z}_C$

$$[a, b] + [c, d] := [a + c, b \oplus d]$$

```
instance
  open import Ops

  Sum $\mathbb{Z}_C$  : Sum  $\mathbb{Z}_C$ 
```

```

_+_ { SumZC } [ a , b ] [ c , d ] = [ a + c , b ⊕ d ]
additive-zero { SumZC } = [ 0Z , zero ]
lemma-sum-zero { SumZC } = cong2 [_,_] lemma-sum-zero lemma-sum-zero

```

```

SubZC : Sub ZC
- _ { SubZC } [ a , b ] = [ - a , b ]

```

$$[a, b] \cdot [c, d] := [a \cdot c, b \cdot d]$$

```

instance
  open import Ops

  MulZC : Mul ZC
  _*_ { MulZC } [ a , b ] [ c , d ] = [ a · c , b · d ]
  unit { MulZC } = [ 1Z , one ]
  lemma-unit { MulZC } = cong2 [_,_] lemma-unit lemma-unit

```

Proof. Now let's check if the given definition is valid:

```

module RingZC where

```

```

-----
-- Properties of + --
-----

+-assoc : (a b c : ZC) → (a + b) + c ≡ a + (b + c)
+-assoc [ va , pa ] [ vb , pb ] [ vc , pc ] =
  cong2 [_,_] (Zp.+-assoc va vb vc) (F2p.⊕-assoc pa pb pc)

+-comm : (a b : ZC) → a + b ≡ b + a
+-comm [ va , pa ] [ vb , pb ] =
  cong2 [_,_] (Zp.+-comm va vb) (F2p.⊕-comm pa pb)

+-identityl : (z : ZC) → additive-zero + z ≡ z
+-identityl _ = lemma-sum-zero
+-identityr : (z : ZC) → z + additive-zero ≡ z
+-identityr z rewrite +-comm z additive-zero = +-identityl z

+-inversel : (z : ZC) → (- z) + z ≡ additive-zero
+-inversel [ v , p ] = cong2 [_,_] (Zp.+-inversel v) (F2p.⊕-self p)
+-inverser : (z : ZC) → z + (- z) ≡ additive-zero
+-inverser [ v , p ] = cong2 [_,_] (Zp.+-inverser v) (F2p.⊕-self p)

-----

```

```

-- Properties of · --
-----

--assoc : (a b c : ℤC) → (a · b) · c ≡ a · (b · c)
--assoc [ va , pa ] [ vb , pb ] [ vc , pc ] =
  cong2 [_,_] (ℤp.*-assoc va vb vc) (℔₂p.∧-assoc pa pb pc)

--comm : (a b : ℤC) → a · b ≡ b · a
--comm [ va , pa ] [ vb , pb ] =
  cong2 [_,_] (ℤp.*-comm va vb) (℔₂p.∧-comm pa pb)

--identityl : (z : ℤC) → unit · z ≡ z
--identityl _ = lemma-unit
--identityr : (z : ℤC) → z · unit ≡ z
--identityr z rewrite ·-comm z unit = ·-identityl z

--distribr+ : (c a b : ℤC) → (a + b) · c ≡ a · c + b · c
--distribr+ [ vc , pc ] [ va , pa ] [ vb , pb ] =
  cong2 [_,_] (ℤp.*-distribr+ vc va vb) (℔₂p.∧-distribr+⊕ pc pa pb)
--distribl+ : (c a b : ℤC) → c · (a + b) ≡ c · a + c · b
--distribl+ c a b rewrite ·-comm c (a + b) | ·-distribr+ c a b =
  (cong2 _+_ (·-comm a c) (·-comm b c))

--zerol : (a : ℤC) → additive-zero · a ≡ additive-zero
--zerol [ v , p ] = cong2 [_,_] (ℤp.*-zerol v) (℔₂p.∧-zerol p)
--zeror : (a : ℤC) → a · additive-zero ≡ additive-zero
--zeror a rewrite ·-comm a additive-zero = ·-zerol a

-----
-- Structures --
-----

ℤC-+-isMagma = record
  { isEquivalence = isEquivalence
  ; ·-cong        = cong2 (_+_ { SumℤC })
  }
ℤC-·-isMagma = record
  { isEquivalence = isEquivalence
  ; ·-cong        = cong2 (_·_ { MulℤC })
  }

ℤC-+-isSemigroup = record
  { isMagma = ℤC-+-isMagma
  ; assoc   = +-assoc
  }
ℤC-·-isSemigroup = record

```

```

{ isMagma = ZC--isMagma
; assoc   = --assoc
}

ZC+-isMonoid = record
{ isSemigroup = ZC+-isSemigroup
; identity    = +-identityl , +-identityr
}
ZC--isMonoid = record
{ isSemigroup = ZC--isSemigroup
; identity    = --identityl , --identityr
}

ZC+-isGroup = record
{ isMonoid = ZC+-isMonoid
; inverse  = +-inversel , +-inverser
; -1-cong = cong (-)
}

ZC+-isAbelianGroup = record
{ isGroup = ZC+-isGroup
; comm    = +-comm
}

ZC-isRing = record
{ +-isAbelianGroup = ZC+-isAbelianGroup
; *-isMonoid       = ZC--isMonoid
; distrib          = --distribl+- , --distribr+-
; zero             = --zerol , --zeror
}

ZC-isCommRing = record
{ isRing = ZC-isRing
; *-comm = --comm
}

```

□

Lemma 1.1 (Powers of complete integers).

$$[v, p]^n = [v^n, p] \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}^+$$

$$[v, p]^0 = [1, 1]$$

Proof.

```

lemma- $\mathbb{ZC}$ -powers : {z :  $\mathbb{ZC}$ } {n :  $\mathbb{N}$ }
  → z ^ n ≡ [ (ZC.val z) ^ n , (ZC.par z) ^ n ]
lemma- $\mathbb{ZC}$ -powers {n = zero}      = refl
lemma- $\mathbb{ZC}$ -powers {z} {N.suc n} = cong (·_ z) $ lemma- $\mathbb{ZC}$ -powers {n = n}

lemma- $\mathbb{ZC}$ -powers-succ : {z :  $\mathbb{ZC}$ } {n :  $\mathbb{N}$ }
  → z ^ N.suc n ≡ [ (ZC.val z) ^ N.suc n , ZC.par z ]
lemma- $\mathbb{ZC}$ -powers-succ {[ _ , p ]} {n}
  = trans (lemma- $\mathbb{ZC}$ -powers {n = N.suc n}) (cong2 [_ , _] refl (F2p.pow p n))

lemma- $\mathbb{ZC}$ -powers-zero : {z :  $\mathbb{ZC}$ } → z ^ zero ≡ unit
lemma- $\mathbb{ZC}$ -powers-zero = refl

```

□

1.1 Value and parity

In this section we will see two functions, that explain the role of v and p , and see their properties.

Definition 1.3 (Value function).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{val} &: \mathbb{Z} \cup \mathbb{Z}_C \rightarrow \mathbb{Z} \\ \text{val}(z) &:= z \quad \forall z \in \mathbb{Z} \\ \text{val}([v, p]) &:= v \quad \forall [v, p] \in \mathbb{Z}_C \end{aligned}$$

```

record Val (A : Set) : Set where
  field
    val : A →  $\mathbb{Z}$ 

open Val { ... }

instance
  Val $\mathbb{Z}$  : Val  $\mathbb{Z}$ 
  val { Val $\mathbb{Z}$  } z = z

instance
  Val $\mathbb{ZC}$  : Val  $\mathbb{ZC}$ 
  val { Val $\mathbb{ZC}$  } = ZC.val

```

Theorem 1.1 (Properties of value). *Given $x, y \in \mathbb{Z} \vee x, y \in \mathbb{Z}_C$ and $z \in \mathbb{Z}$*

1. Value is odd.

$$\text{val}(-x) = -\text{val}(x)$$

th-val-odd- \mathbb{Z} : {x : \mathbb{Z} } → val (- x) ≡ - val x
th-val-odd- \mathbb{Z} = refl

th-val-odd- $\mathbb{Z}C$: {x : $\mathbb{Z}C$ } → val (- x) ≡ - val x
th-val-odd- $\mathbb{Z}C$ = refl

2. *Linearity.*

$$\text{val}(x + y) = \text{val}(x) + \text{val}(y)$$

$$\text{val}(z \cdot x) = z \text{val}(x)$$

th-val-linearity- \mathbb{Z} : {x y : \mathbb{Z} } → val (x + y) ≡ val x + val y
th-val-linearity- \mathbb{Z} = refl

th-val-homogeneity- \mathbb{Z} : {x z : \mathbb{Z} } → val (z · x) ≡ z · val x
th-val-homogeneity- \mathbb{Z} = refl

th-val-linearity- $\mathbb{Z}C$: {x y : $\mathbb{Z}C$ } → val (x + y) ≡ val x + val y
th-val-linearity- $\mathbb{Z}C$ = refl

th-val-homogeneity \mathbb{N} - $\mathbb{Z}C$: {x : $\mathbb{Z}C$ } {n : \mathbb{N} } → val (n × x) ≡ $\mathbb{Z}.\text{pos } n \cdot \text{val } x$
th-val-homogeneity \mathbb{N} - $\mathbb{Z}C$ {n = zero} = refl
th-val-homogeneity \mathbb{N} - $\mathbb{Z}C$ {x} { $\mathbb{N}.\text{suc } n$ } = begin
 val ($\mathbb{N}.\text{suc } n \times x$) ≡⟨⟩
 val (x + n × x) ≡⟨ *th-val-linearity- $\mathbb{Z}C$* {x} {n × x} ⟩
 val x + val (n × x) ≡⟨ cong (λ_ (val x)) \$
 th-val-homogeneity \mathbb{N} - $\mathbb{Z}C$ {x} {n} ⟩
 val x + $\mathbb{Z}.\text{pos } n \cdot \text{val } x$ ≡⟨ cong (λ_ + $\mathbb{Z}.\text{pos } n \cdot \text{val } x$) \$
 sym ($\mathbb{Z}p.*\text{-identity}$ (val x)) ⟩
 $1\mathbb{Z} \cdot \text{val } x + \mathbb{Z}.\text{pos } n \cdot \text{val } x$ ≡⟨ $\mathbb{Z}p.*\text{-distrib}$ (val x) $1\mathbb{Z}$ ($\mathbb{Z}.\text{pos } n$) ⟩
 ($1\mathbb{Z} + \mathbb{Z}.\text{pos } n$) · val x ≡⟨⟩
 $\mathbb{Z}.\text{pos } (\mathbb{N}.\text{suc } n) \cdot \text{val } x$ ■

th-val-homogeneity- $\mathbb{Z}C$: {x : $\mathbb{Z}C$ } {z : \mathbb{Z} } → val (z × x) ≡ z · val x
th-val-homogeneity- $\mathbb{Z}C$ {z = $\mathbb{Z}.\text{pos } n$ } = cong val (*th-val-homogeneity \mathbb{N} - $\mathbb{Z}C$* {n = n})
th-val-homogeneity- $\mathbb{Z}C$ {x} {-[1+ n]} = begin
 val (-[1+ n] × x) ≡⟨⟩
 val (- ($\mathbb{N}.\text{suc } n \times x$)) ≡⟨⟩
 - val ($\mathbb{N}.\text{suc } n \times x$) ≡⟨ cong (-) \$ *th-val-homogeneity \mathbb{N} - $\mathbb{Z}C$* {n = $\mathbb{N}.\text{suc } n$ } ⟩

$$\begin{aligned}
- (+[1+ n] \cdot \text{val } x) &\equiv \langle \mathbb{Z}p.\text{neg-distrib}^l \cdot * +[1+ n] (\text{val } x) \rangle \\
(- +[1+ n]) \cdot \text{val } x &\equiv \langle \rangle \\
-[1+ n] \cdot \text{val } x &\blacksquare
\end{aligned}$$

3. Idempotence of the value.

$$\text{val} \circ \text{val} = \text{val}$$

th-val-idempotence : $\{A : \text{Set}\} \{ _ : \text{Val } A \} \{x : A\} \rightarrow \text{val} (\text{val } x) \equiv \text{val } x$
th-val-idempotence = *refl*

4. Completely multiplicative.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{val}(1) &= \text{val}([1, 1]) = 1 \\
\text{val}(x \cdot y) &= \text{val}(x) \cdot \text{val}(y)
\end{aligned}$$

th-val-mul-unit- \mathbb{Z} : $\text{val } \{\mathbb{Z}\} \text{unit} \equiv 1\mathbb{Z}$
th-val-mul-unit- \mathbb{Z} = *refl*

th-val-mul-unit- $\mathbb{Z}C$: $\text{val } \{\mathbb{Z}C\} \text{unit} \equiv 1\mathbb{Z}$
th-val-mul-unit- $\mathbb{Z}C$ = *refl*

th-val-mul- \mathbb{Z} : $\{x \ y : \mathbb{Z}\} \rightarrow \text{val} (x \cdot y) \equiv \text{val } x \cdot \text{val } y$
th-val-mul- \mathbb{Z} = *refl*

th-val-mul- $\mathbb{Z}C$: $\{x \ y : \mathbb{Z}C\} \rightarrow \text{val} (x \cdot y) \equiv \text{val } x \cdot \text{val } y$
th-val-mul- $\mathbb{Z}C$ = *refl*

Definition 1.4 (Parity function).

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{par} : \mathbb{Z} \cup \mathbb{Z}C &\rightarrow \mathbb{F}_2 \\
\text{par}(z) &:= \begin{cases} 0 & z \text{ even} \\ 1 & z \text{ odd} \end{cases} \quad \forall z \in \mathbb{Z} \\
\text{par}([v, p]) &:= p \quad \forall [v, p] \in \mathbb{Z}C
\end{aligned}$$

record Par (A : Set) : Set **where**
field
 par : A → \mathbb{F}_2

open Par { ... }

```
instance
  ParZ : Par ℤ
  par { ParZ } z with even-or-odd z
  ... | even _ = zero
  ... | odd _ = one
```

```
instance
  ParZC : Par ℤC
  par { ParZC } = ℤC.par
```

A useful lemma for future proofs on parity in \mathbb{Z}

```
parity-even : {z : ℤ} → Even z → par z ≡ zero
parity-even p rewrite lemma-even p = refl
```

```
parity-odd : {z : ℤ} → Odd z → par z ≡ one
parity-odd p rewrite lemma-odd p = refl
```

```
parity-even-1 : {z : ℤ} → par z ≡ zero → Even z
parity-even-1 {z} parz≡0 with even-or-odd z
... | even p = p
... | odd p with parz≡0
... | ()
```

Theorem 1.2 (Properties of parity). *Given $x, y \in \mathbb{Z} \vee x, y \in \mathbb{Z}_C$ and $z \in \mathbb{Z}$*

1. *Parity is even.*

$$\text{par}(-x) = \text{par}(x)$$

```
th-par-even-ℤ : {x : ℤ} → par (- x) ≡ par x
th-par-even-ℤ {x} with even-or-odd x
... | even p = parity-even (neg-even p)
... | odd p = parity-odd (neg-odd p)
```

```
th-par-even-ℤC : {x : ℤC} → par (- x) ≡ par x
th-par-even-ℤC = refl
```

2. *Linearity.*

Since $\text{par}(x) \in \mathbb{F}_2$ the sum operator must be replaced by exclusive or (\oplus).

$$\text{par}(x + y) = \text{par}(x) \oplus \text{par}(y)$$

```

th-par-linearity-ℤ : {x y : ℤ} → par (x + y) ≡ par x ⊕ par y
th-par-linearity-ℤ {x} {y} with even-or-odd x | even-or-odd y
... | even p | even q = parity-even $ sum-even-even p q
... | even p | odd q = parity-odd $ sum-even-odd p q
... | odd p | even q = parity-odd $ sum-odd-even p q
... | odd p | odd q = parity-even $ sum-odd-odd p q

```

```

th-par-linearity-ℤC : {x y : ℤC} → par (x + y) ≡ par x ⊕ par y
th-par-linearity-ℤC = refl

```

3. Idempotence of the parity.

$$\text{par} \circ \text{par} = \text{par}$$

To prove this we need to extend the parity to \mathbb{F}_2 (Agda does not know $\mathbb{F}_2 \subset \mathbb{Z}$)

instance

```

Parℱ₂ : Par ℱ₂
par { Parℱ₂ } zero = par 0ℤ
par { Parℱ₂ } one = par 1ℤ

```

```

th-par-idempotence : {A : Set} { _ : Par A } {x : A} → par (par x) ≡ par x
th-par-idempotence {x = x} with par x
... | zero = refl
... | one = refl

```

4. Completely multiplicative.

$$\text{par}(1) = 1$$

$$\text{par}(x \cdot y) = \text{par}(x) \cdot \text{par}(y)$$

```

th-par-mul-unit-ℤ : par {ℤ} unit ≡ one
th-par-mul-unit-ℤ = refl

```

```

th-par-mul-unit-ℤC : par {ℤC} unit ≡ one
th-par-mul-unit-ℤC = refl

```

```

th-par-mul-ℤ : {x y : ℤ} → par (x · y) ≡ par x · par y
th-par-mul-ℤ {x} {y} with even-or-odd x | even-or-odd y
... | even p | even q = parity-even $ mul-even-even p q

```

```

... | even p | odd q = parity-even $ mul-even-odd p q
... | odd p | even q = parity-even $ mul-odd-even p q
... | odd p | odd q = parity-odd $ mul-odd-odd p q

```

```

th-par-mul-ℤC : {x y : ℤC} → par (x · y) ≡ par x · par y
th-par-mul-ℤC = refl

```

Lemma 1.2 (Parity of powers).

$$\text{par}(z^n) = \text{par}(z) \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}^+$$

Proof.

```

par-pow-ℤ : {z : ℤ} {n : ℕ} → par (z ^ ℕ.suc n) ≡ par z
par-pow-ℤ {z} {0} rewrite ℤp.*-identity z = refl
par-pow-ℤ {z} {ℕ.suc n} = begin
  par (z ^ ℕ.suc (ℕ.suc n)) ≡⟨
  par (z · z ^ ℕ.suc n)      ≡⟨ th-par-mul-ℤ {z} {z ^ ℕ.suc n} ⟩
  par z · par (z ^ ℕ.suc n) ≡⟨ cong (·_) (par z) ⟩ $ par-pow-ℤ {z} {n} ⟩
  par z · par z              ≡⟨ ℤp.∧-idem (par z) ⟩
  par z                      ■

```

```

par-pow-ℤC : {z : ℤC} {n : ℕ} → par (z ^ ℕ.suc n) ≡ par z
par-pow-ℤC {z} {0}          = ℤp.∧-identity (par z)
par-pow-ℤC {z} {ℕ.suc n} = begin
  par (z ^ ℕ.suc (ℕ.suc n)) ≡⟨
  par (z · z ^ ℕ.suc n)      ≡⟨ th-par-mul-ℤC {z} {z ^ ℕ.suc n} ⟩
  par z · par (z ^ ℕ.suc n) ≡⟨ cong (·_) (par z) ⟩ $ par-pow-ℤC {z} {n} ⟩
  par z · par z              ≡⟨ ℤp.∧-idem (par z) ⟩
  par z                      ■

```

□

1.2 Related sets

Definition 1.5 (Integers prime). Let us define the set of integers prime as

$$\mathbb{Z}' := \{[v, p] \in \mathbb{Z}_C : p = \text{par}(v)\} = \{[v, \text{par}(v)] : v \in \mathbb{Z}\}$$

\mathbb{Z}' : Set

$\mathbb{Z}' = \Sigma[([v, p]) \in \mathbb{Z}_C] p \equiv \text{par } v$

$\mathbb{Z}'\text{-eq} : \{a b : \mathbb{Z}'\} \rightarrow \text{proj}_1 a \equiv \text{proj}_1 b \rightarrow a \equiv b$

$\mathbb{Z}'\text{-eq} \{_, \text{refl}\} \{_, \text{refl}\} \text{refl} = \text{refl}$

Definition 1.6 (Dis-integers). Let us define the set of dis-integers as

$$\mathbb{Z}_D := \{[v, p] \in \mathbb{Z}_C : p \neq \text{par}(v)\}$$

\mathbb{Z}_D : Set

$$\mathbb{Z}_D = \Sigma [([v, p]) \in \mathbb{Z}_C] p \equiv \neg (\text{par } v)$$

Remark. $\{\mathbb{Z}', \mathbb{Z}_D\}$ is a partition of \mathbb{Z}_C .

$$\mathbb{Z}' \sqcup \mathbb{Z}_D = \mathbb{Z}_C$$

Theorem 1.3 (Integers and integers prime are isomorphic). *The function $f_{\mathbb{Z}} : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}'$ defined as*

$$f_{\mathbb{Z}}(z) = [z, \text{par}(z)]$$

is an isomorphism.

$f_{\mathbb{Z}} : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}'$

$$f_{\mathbb{Z}} z = [z, \text{par } z], \text{ refl}$$

$f_{\mathbb{Z}}^{-1} : \mathbb{Z}' \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$

$$f_{\mathbb{Z}}^{-1} ([z, _], _) = z$$

Proof. Before proving this we have to say to Agda to use on \mathbb{Z}' the same operations of \mathbb{Z}_C

instance

$\text{Sum}\mathbb{Z}' : \text{Sum } \mathbb{Z}'$

$$\begin{aligned} _+_ \{ \text{Sum}\mathbb{Z}' \} (a, \text{ refl}) (b, \text{ refl}) &= \\ & a + b, \text{ sym } (\text{th-par-linearity-}\mathbb{Z} \{ \text{val } a \}) \\ \text{additive-zero } \{ \text{Sum}\mathbb{Z}' \} &= \text{additive-zero}, \text{ refl} \\ \text{lemma-sum-zero } \{ \text{Sum}\mathbb{Z}' \} \{ [v, _] , \text{ refl} \} &= \\ & \mathbb{Z}'\text{-eq } (\text{cong } [_, \text{par } v] \$ \text{lemma-sum-zero } \{\mathbb{Z}\}) \end{aligned}$$

$\text{Mul}\mathbb{Z}' : \text{Mul } \mathbb{Z}'$

$$\begin{aligned} _ \cdot _ \{ \text{Mul}\mathbb{Z}' \} (a, \text{ refl}) (b, \text{ refl}) &= \\ & a \cdot b, \text{ sym } (\text{th-par-mul-}\mathbb{Z} \{ \text{val } a \}) \\ \text{unit } \{ \text{Mul}\mathbb{Z}' \} &= \text{unit}, \text{ refl} \\ \text{lemma-unit } \{ \text{Mul}\mathbb{Z}' \} \{ [v, _] , \text{ refl} \} &= \\ & \mathbb{Z}'\text{-eq } (\text{cong } [_, \text{par } v] \$ \text{lemma-unit } \{\mathbb{Z}\}) \end{aligned}$$

module isomorphism-f \mathbb{Z} where

 -- $f_{\mathbb{Z}}$ homomorphism --

```

-----

addition : {a b : ℤ} → fℤ (a + b) ≡ fℤ a + fℤ b
addition {a} {b} rewrite sym $ th-par-linearity-ℤ {a} {b} = refl

multiplication : {a b : ℤ} → fℤ (a · b) ≡ fℤ a · fℤ b
multiplication {a} {b} rewrite sym $ th-par-mul-ℤ {a} {b} = refl

mul-identity : fℤ unit ≡ unit
mul-identity = refl

-----
-- fℤ isomorphism --
-----

fℤofℤ-1≡id : {z : ℤ'} → fℤ (fℤ-1 z) ≡ z
fℤofℤ-1≡id {[ v , _ ] , refl} = ℤ'-eq refl

fℤ-1ofℤ≡id : {z : ℤ} → fℤ-1 (fℤ z) ≡ z
fℤ-1ofℤ≡id = refl

```

□

Since \mathbb{Z}' is isomorphic to \mathbb{Z} , and so the two cannot be distinguished, we won't write \mathbb{Z}' anymore and we will use the notation $[v, \text{par}(v)]$ to denote elements in \mathbb{Z} too.

More precisely we will write, with an abuse of notation, $\mathbb{Z}' = \mathbb{Z}$ and $[v, \text{par}(v)] = v$ meaning respectively $\mathbb{Z}' = f_{\mathbb{Z}}(\mathbb{Z})$ and $[v, \text{par}(v)] = f_{\mathbb{Z}}(v)$.

1.2.1 Dis-integers

We said in the introduction that dis-integers are the dual of integers along parity, in fact in \mathbb{Z}_D we have $[0, 1]$ which has null value and odd parity, $[1, 0]$ which has unitary value, but even parity, and in general $[v, p]$ where the parity p is not the parity of the integer v .

Definition 1.7 (Odd zero). Let's call $o := [0, 1]$ the *odd zero*, since it has null value and odd parity.

```

o : ℤC
o = [ 0ℤ , one ]

```

Lemma 1.3 (Swap parity). *Summing the odd zero to a complete integer its parity changes.*

Proof.

```

swap-parity : (z : ℤC) → par z ≡ ¬ (par (z + o))
swap-parity [ _ , zero ] = refl
swap-parity [ _ , one ] = refl

```

□

Definition 1.8 (Even unit). Let's call $l := [1, 0]$ the *even unit*, since it has unitary value and even parity.

```

l : ℤC
l = [ 1ℤ , zero ]

```

Lemma 1.4 (Change only value). *Summing the even unit to a complete integer only it's value changes, not its parity.*

Proof.

```

par[z+1] : (z : ℤC) → par (z + 1) ≡ par z
par[z+1] [ _ , zero ] = refl
par[z+1] [ _ , one ] = refl

val[z+1] : (z : ℤC) → val (z + 1) ≡ val z + 1ℤ
val[z+1] [ v , _ ] = refl

par[z-1] : (z : ℤC) → par (z - 1) ≡ par z
par[z-1] [ _ , zero ] = refl
par[z-1] [ _ , one ] = refl

val[z-1] : (z : ℤC) → val (z - 1) ≡ val z - 1ℤ
val[z-1] [ v , _ ] = refl

```

□

Lemma 1.5 (Dis-integer as integer plus odd unit). *Each dis-integer can be written as the sum of an integer with l .*

Proof.

```

 $\mathbb{Z}D\text{-from-}\mathbb{Z}+1 : ((a, _) : \mathbb{Z}D) \rightarrow \Sigma[(b, _) \in \mathbb{Z}'] a \equiv b + 1$ 
 $\mathbb{Z}D\text{-from-}\mathbb{Z}+1 (a, q) = (a - 1, \text{help}_1 (a, q)), \text{help}_2 a$ 
  where
   $\text{help}_1 : ((z, _) : \mathbb{Z}D) \rightarrow \text{par } (z - 1) \equiv \text{par } (\text{val } (z - 1))$ 
   $\text{help}_1 (z@([v, _]), \text{refl}) \text{rewrite } \text{par}[z-1] z$ 
    |  $\text{th-par-linearity-}\mathbb{Z} \{v\} \{-1\mathbb{Z}\} \text{with } \text{par } v$ 
  ... |  $\text{zero} = \text{refl}$ 
  ... |  $\text{one} = \text{refl}$ 
   $\text{help}_2 : (z : \mathbb{Z}C) \rightarrow z \equiv (z - 1) + 1$ 
   $\text{help}_2 z \text{rewrite } \text{val}[z-1] z \mid \text{par}[z-1] z \mid \text{val}[z+1] (z - 1) \mid \text{par}[z+1] (z - 1) =$ 
     $\text{cong}_2 [_ , _] (\text{sym } \$ \text{trans } (\mathbb{Z}p.\text{+-assoc } (\text{val } z) (-1\mathbb{Z}) 1\mathbb{Z})$ 
       $(\mathbb{Z}p.\text{+-identity}'' (\text{val } z)))$ 
     $(\mathbb{F}_2p.\oplus\text{-comm } \text{zero } (\text{par } z))$ 

```

□

1.3 Behaviours induced by parity

We now will show how the parity of a complete integer is not a mere binary flag, but induces the same properties of even and odd numbers into \mathbb{Z}_C : complete integers with even parity act like even numbers and those with odd parity like odd numbers.

```

data  $\mathbb{Z}C\text{-Even} : \mathbb{Z}C \rightarrow \text{Set}$  where
  even :  $\{z : \mathbb{Z}C\} \rightarrow \text{par } z \equiv \text{zero} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}C\text{-Even } z$ 

data  $\mathbb{Z}C\text{-Odd} : \mathbb{Z}C \rightarrow \text{Set}$  where
  odd :  $\{z : \mathbb{Z}C\} \rightarrow \text{par } z \equiv \text{one} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}C\text{-Odd } z$ 

```

Lemma 1.6 (Parity of integers is preserved). *The usual notion of parity in \mathbb{Z} and this new notion of parity in \mathbb{Z}_C are the same for integer numbers.*

Proof.

```

even $\mathbb{Z} \Rightarrow$ even $\mathbb{Z}C : \{z : \mathbb{Z}\} \rightarrow \text{Even } z \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}C\text{-Even } (\text{proj}_1 (f\mathbb{Z} z))$ 
even $\mathbb{Z} \Rightarrow$ even $\mathbb{Z}C p = \text{even } (\text{parity-even } p)$ 

odd $\mathbb{Z} \Rightarrow$ odd $\mathbb{Z}C : \{z : \mathbb{Z}\} \rightarrow \text{Odd } z \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}C\text{-Odd } (\text{proj}_1 (f\mathbb{Z} z))$ 
odd $\mathbb{Z} \Rightarrow$ odd $\mathbb{Z}C p = \text{odd } (\text{parity-odd } p)$ 

even $\mathbb{Z}C \Rightarrow$ even $\mathbb{Z} : \{z : \mathbb{Z}'\} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}C\text{-Even } (\text{proj}_1 z) \rightarrow \text{Even } (f\mathbb{Z}^{-1} z)$ 
even $\mathbb{Z}C \Rightarrow$ even $\mathbb{Z} \{z\} (\text{even } \_) \text{rewrite } \text{proj}_2 z \text{with } \text{even-or-odd } (f\mathbb{Z}^{-1} z)$ 

```

... | even $q = q$

`odd $\mathbb{Z}C \Rightarrow$ odd \mathbb{Z} : {z : \mathbb{Z}' } \rightarrow $\mathbb{Z}C$ -Odd (proj1 z) \rightarrow Odd (f \mathbb{Z}^{-1} z)
 odd $\mathbb{Z}C \Rightarrow$ odd \mathbb{Z} {z} (odd _) rewrite proj2 z with even-or-odd (f \mathbb{Z}^{-1} z)
 ... | odd $q = q$`

□

Lemma 1.7 (Parity of addition).

even + even = even

even + odd = odd

odd + even = odd

odd + odd = even

Proof.

`sum- $\mathbb{Z}C$ -even-even : {x y : $\mathbb{Z}C$ } \rightarrow $\mathbb{Z}C$ -Even x \rightarrow $\mathbb{Z}C$ -Even y \rightarrow $\mathbb{Z}C$ -Even (x + y)
 sum- $\mathbb{Z}C$ -even-even (even refl) (even refl) = even refl`

`sum- $\mathbb{Z}C$ -even-odd : {x y : $\mathbb{Z}C$ } \rightarrow $\mathbb{Z}C$ -Even x \rightarrow $\mathbb{Z}C$ -Odd y \rightarrow $\mathbb{Z}C$ -Odd (x + y)
 sum- $\mathbb{Z}C$ -even-odd (even refl) (odd refl) = odd refl`

`sum- $\mathbb{Z}C$ -odd-even : {x y : $\mathbb{Z}C$ } \rightarrow $\mathbb{Z}C$ -Odd x \rightarrow $\mathbb{Z}C$ -Even y \rightarrow $\mathbb{Z}C$ -Odd (x + y)
 sum- $\mathbb{Z}C$ -odd-even (odd refl) (even refl) = odd refl`

`sum- $\mathbb{Z}C$ -odd-odd : {x y : $\mathbb{Z}C$ } \rightarrow $\mathbb{Z}C$ -Odd x \rightarrow $\mathbb{Z}C$ -Odd y \rightarrow $\mathbb{Z}C$ -Even (x + y)
 sum- $\mathbb{Z}C$ -odd-odd (odd refl) (odd refl) = even refl`

□

Lemma 1.8 (Parity of multiplication).

even · even = even

even · odd = even

odd · even = even

odd · odd = odd

Proof.

`mul- \mathbb{ZC} -even-even` : {x y : \mathbb{ZC} } → \mathbb{ZC} -Even x → \mathbb{ZC} -Even y → \mathbb{ZC} -Even (x · y)
`mul- \mathbb{ZC} -even-even` (even refl) (even refl) = even refl

`mul- \mathbb{ZC} -even-odd` : {x y : \mathbb{ZC} } → \mathbb{ZC} -Even x → \mathbb{ZC} -Odd y → \mathbb{ZC} -Even (x · y)
`mul- \mathbb{ZC} -even-odd` (even refl) (odd refl) = even refl

`mul- \mathbb{ZC} -odd-even` : {x y : \mathbb{ZC} } → \mathbb{ZC} -Odd x → \mathbb{ZC} -Even y → \mathbb{ZC} -Even (x · y)
`mul- \mathbb{ZC} -odd-even` (odd refl) (even refl) = even refl

`mul- \mathbb{ZC} -odd-odd` : {x y : \mathbb{ZC} } → \mathbb{ZC} -Odd x → \mathbb{ZC} -Odd y → \mathbb{ZC} -Odd (x · y)
`mul- \mathbb{ZC} -odd-odd` (odd refl) (odd refl) = odd refl

□

1.4 Reals exponentiation to the power of complete integers

In this section we will define an exponentiation function with real bases and complete integer exponents.

To help us come up with a good definition we can split on the exponent z :

1. If z is an integer, this operation is already defined as x^z for $x \in \mathbb{R}$;
2. If z is a dis-integer, we know from lemma 1.5 that there exist an integer $y = z - l$ s.t. $z = y + l$; supposing that our function respects exponent rules (which we will prove in theorem 1.4), we can write $x^z = z^{y+l} = z^y \cdot z^l$.

So all we have to do is to define the value of x^l .

If we pick an $x \in \mathbb{R}$ we can intuitively say that x^l should be equal to $|x|$ because:

1. being the parity of l even, x^l should be an even function of x ;
2. being the value of l one, x^l should be a somewhat linear function.

So our definition, for $x \in \mathbb{R}$ and $z \in \mathbb{Z}_C$, would be:

$$x^z = \begin{cases} \text{usual } x^z & z \in \mathbb{Z} \\ x^y \cdot x^l = x^y \cdot |x| & z \in \mathbb{Z}_D \end{cases}$$

with $y = z - l \in \mathbb{Z}$

We will instead use another definition, and later prove they are equal.

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Definition 1.9 (Real exponentiation to complete integers). For $x \in \mathbb{R}$ and $z \in \mathbb{Z}_C$, we define

$$x^z = x^{\text{val}(z)-k} |x|^k$$

with $k = \text{par}(\text{val}(z)) \oplus \text{par}(z)$.

```
F2-to-ℤ : ℱ2 → ℤ
F2-to-ℤ zero = 0ℤ
F2-to-ℤ one  = 1ℤ
```

instance

```
CIPowℝ\0 : CertPow ℝ ℤC {NonZero} {ℝ}
  ^_ { CIPowℝ\0 } x [ v , p ] = let k = F2-to-ℤ (par v ⊕ p) in
    x ^ (v - k) · | x | ^ k
```

Proof.

```
pow-def-eq-ℤ : (z : ℤ) → (x : ℝ) .{ _ : NonZero x } →
  x ^ proj1 (fℤ z) ≡ x ^ z
pow-def-eq-ℤ z x rewrite ℱ2p.⊕-self (par z) | ℤp.+--identityr z =
  ℝp.*-identityr (x ^ z)
```

```
pow-def-eq-ℤD : (z : ℤD) → (x : ℝ) .{ _ : NonZero x } → let
  y = fℤ-1 (proj1 (ℤD-from-ℤ+1 z))
in x ^ proj1 z ≡ x ^ y · | x |
pow-def-eq-ℤD ([ v , _ ] , refl) x rewrite sym (ℱ2p.↔-distribr-⊕ (par v) (par v))
  | ℱ2p.⊕-self (par v) = cong (· (x ^ (v - 1ℤ))) $ ℝp.*-identityr | x |
```

□

Theorem 1.4 (Exponent rules). *Definition 1.9 respects exponent rules, i.e. for $x, y \in \mathbb{R}$ and $z, w \in \mathbb{Z}_C$*

$$x^{z+w} = x^z \cdot x^w; \quad (x \cdot y)^z = x^z \cdot y^z; \quad (x^z)^w = x^{zw}$$

Proof.

```
k-of-sum : (z w : ℤC) → par (val (z + w)) ⊕ par (z + w) ≡ let
  kz = par (val z) ⊕ par z; kw = par (val w) ⊕ par w in kz ⊕ kw
k-of-sum z w rewrite th-par-linearity-ℤ {val z} {val w}
  = ℱ2p.⊕-comm-middle (par (val z)) (par (val w)) (par z) (par w)
```

private

```

sum-exp-helper : (x : ℝ) .{ _ : NonZero x } → (z w : ℤ) →
  x ^ ((z + w) + -[1+ 0 ]) · (| x | · 1ℝ) ≡
  (x ^ (z + 0ℤ) · 1ℝ) · (x ^ (w + -[1+ 0 ]) · (| x | · 1ℝ))
sum-exp-helper x z w rewrite ℤp.+-identity" z | ℝp.*-identity" (x ^ z)
  | sym (ℝp.*-assoc (x ^ z) (x ^ (w + -[1+ 0 ]))) (| x | · 1ℝ)
  | ℤp.+-assoc z w -[1+ 0 ] =
  cong (· (| x | · 1ℝ)) $ ℝp.sum-exp x z (w + -[1+ 0 ])

sum-exp : (x : ℝ) .{ _ : NonZero x } → (z w : ℤC) →
  x ^ (z + w) ≡ x ^ z · x ^ w
sum-exp x z w rewrite k-of-sum z w with par (val z) ⊕ par z
  | par (val w) ⊕ par w
... | zero | zero rewrite ℤp.+-identity" (val z + val w) | ℤp.+-identity" (val z)
  | ℤp.+-identity" (val w) | ℝp.*-identity" (x ^ (val z + val w))
  | ℝp.*-identity" (x ^ val z) | ℝp.*-identity" (x ^ val w)
  = ℝp.sum-exp x (val z) (val w)
... | zero | one = sum-exp-helper x (val z) (val w)
... | one | zero rewrite ℤp.+-comm (val z) (val w)
  | ℝp.*-comm (x ^ (val z + -[1+ 0 ]) · (| x | · 1ℝ)) (x ^ (val w + 0ℤ) · 1ℝ) =
  sum-exp-helper x (val w) (val z)
... | one | one rewrite ℝp.*-identity" | x |
  | ℝp.*-comm-middle (x ^ (val z + -[1+ 0 ])) (| x |)
  (x ^ (val w + -[1+ 0 ])) (| x |)
  | ℝp.|x||x| x | sym $ ℝp.sum-exp x (val z + -[1+ 0 ]) (val w + -[1+ 0 ])
  | ℤp.+-comm-middle (val z) -[1+ 0 ] (val w) -[1+ 0 ]
  | ℝp.*-identity" (x ^ ((val z + val w) + 0ℤ)) = sym $ trans
  (sym $ ℝp.sum-exp x ((val z + val w) + -[1+ 1 ]) 2ℤ)
  (ℝp.^-cong refl $ ℤp.+-assoc (val z + val w) -[1+ 1 ] 2ℤ)

mul-base : (x y : ℝ) .{ p : NonZero x } .{ q : NonZero y } → (z : ℤC) → let
  r = ℝp.x·y-nonZero { p } { q }
  in ((x · y) ^ z) { r } ≡ x ^ z · y ^ z
mul-base x y z with par (val z) ⊕ par z
... | zero rewrite ℤp.+-identity" (val z) | ℝp.*-identity" (x ^ val z)
  | ℝp.*-identity" (y ^ val z) | ℝp.*-identity" ((x · y) ^ val z) { _ } =
  ℝp.mul-base x y (val z)
... | one rewrite ℝp.*-identity" | x | | ℝp.*-identity" | y |
  | ℝp.*-identity" | x · y | | ℝp.*-comm-middle (x ^ (val z - 1ℤ)) (| x |)
  (y ^ (val z - 1ℤ)) | y | | ℝp.|x||y| x y = cong (· | x · y |) $
  ℝp.mul-base x y (val z - 1ℤ)

x^zc≠0 : {x : ℝ} → (q : x ≠ 0) → (z : ℤC) → (x ^ z) { ≠-nonZero q } ≠ 0
x^zc≠0 {x} q [ v , p ] = ℝp.x·y≠0 (ℝp.x^z≠0 q (v - k)) (ℝp.x^z≠0 (|x|≠0 q) k)
where
k = ℔2-to-ℤ (par v ⊕ p)

```

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instance

```
xzc-nonZero : {x : ℝ} .{ _ : NonZero x } → {z : ℤC} → NonZero (x ^ z)
xzc-nonZero { p } { z } = ≠-nonZero $ xzc≠0 (≠-nonZero-1 p) z
```

double-exp : (x : ℝ) .{ q : NonZero x } → (z w : ℤC) → **let**

```
  r = xzc-nonZero { q } { z }
```

```
  in ((x ^ z) ^ w) { r } ≡ x ^ (z · w)
```

double-exp x { q } z@[v₁ , p₁] w@[v₂ , p₂] = **begin**

```
((x ^ (v1 - k1) · | x | ^ k1) ^ w) { _ }
```

```
≡⟨ mul-base (x ^ (v1 - k1)) (| x | ^ k1) { _ } { _ } w ⟩
```

```
((x ^ (v1 - k1)) ^ w) { _ } · ((| x | ^ k1) ^ w) { _ }
```

```
≡⟨ cong2 _ _ (help1 x (v1 - k1) w) (help1 | x | k1 w) ⟩
```

```
(x ^ ([ v1 - k1 , p ] · w)) · (| x | ^ ([ k1 , par k1 ] · w))
```

```
≡⟨ ⟩
```

```
x ^ [ v3 , p · p2 ] · | x | ^ [ v4 , p4 ]
```

```
≡⟨ ⟩
```

```
(x ^ (v3 - k3) · | x | ^ k3) · (| x | ^ (v4 - k4) · | x | ^ k4)
```

```
≡⟨ (cong (λ y → (x ^ (v3 - k3) · | x | ^ k3) ·
```

```
(| x | ^ (v4 - k4) · y)) $ ℝp.^-cong {z = k4} (ℝp.||x|| x) refl) ⟩
```

```
(x ^ (v3 - k3) · | x | ^ k3) · (| x | ^ (v4 - k4) · | x | ^ k4)
```

```
≡⟨ (cong (_ _ (x ^ (v3 - k3) · | x | ^ k3)) $
```

```
trans (sym $ ℝp.sum-exp | x | (v4 - k4) k4)
```

```
(cong (λ (e : ℤ) → | x | ^ e) (begin
```

```
(v4 - k4) + k4 ≡⟨ ℤp.+assoc v4 (- k4) k4 ⟩
```

```
v4 + (- k4 + k4) ≡⟨ (cong (_ + v4) $ ℤp.+inverse' k4) ⟩
```

```
v4 + 0ℤ ≡⟨ ℤp.+identityr v4 ⟩
```

```
v4 ■)))) ⟩
```

```
(x ^ (v3 - k3) · | x | ^ k3) · | x | ^ v4
```

```
≡⟨ ℝp.*-assoc (x ^ (v3 - k3)) (| x | ^ k3) (| x | ^ v4) ⟩
```

```
x ^ (v3 - k3) · (| x | ^ k3 · | x | ^ v4)
```

```
≡⟨ (cong (_ _ (x ^ (v3 - k3))) $ ℝp.sum-exp | x | k3 v4) ⟩
```

```
x ^ (v3 - k3) · | x | ^ (k3 + v4)
```

```
≡⟨ help4 ⟩
```

```
x ^ (v12 - k12) · | x | ^ k12 ■
```

where

```
k1 = F2-to-ℤ (par v1 ⊕ p1)
```

```
k2 = F2-to-ℤ (par v2 ⊕ p2)
```

```
p = par (v1 - k1)
```

```
v12 = v1 · v2
```

```
p12 = p1 · p2
```

```
k12 = F2-to-ℤ (par v12 ⊕ p12)
```

```
v3 = (v1 - k1) · v2
```

```
p3 = p · p2
```

```
k3 = F2-to-ℤ (par v3 ⊕ p3)
```

```
v4 = k1 · v2
```

```
p4 = par k1 · p2
k4 =  $\mathbb{F}_2$ -to- $\mathbb{Z}$  (par v4  $\oplus$  p4)
```

```
help-kz : (z v :  $\mathbb{Z}$ ) → (p :  $\mathbb{F}_2$ ) → let
  k = par v  $\oplus$  p
  in par (z · v)  $\oplus$  par z · p  $\equiv$  par z · k
help-kz z v p = begin
  par (z · v)  $\oplus$  par z · p  $\equiv$  ( cong ( $\_ \oplus$  par z · p) $ th-par-mul- $\mathbb{Z}$  {z} {v}) )
  par z · par v  $\oplus$  par z · p  $\equiv$  (  $\mathbb{F}_2$ p. $\wedge$ -distribl- $\oplus$  (par z) (par v) p )
  par z · (par v  $\oplus$  p) ■
```

```
help0 : (x :  $\mathbb{R}$ ) .{ _ : NonZero x } → {z :  $\mathbb{Z}$ } → Even z → | x ^ z |  $\equiv$  x ^ z
help0 x {z} p with half-even p
... | z/2 , 2z/2 $\equiv$ z = begin
  | x ^ z |  $\equiv$  ( cong |_ $_$  $  $\mathbb{R}$ p. $\wedge$ -cong refl 2z/2 $\equiv$ z )
  | x ^ (2 $\mathbb{Z}$  · z/2) |  $\equiv$  (  $\mathbb{R}$ p.|x2z| x z/2 )
  x ^ (2 $\mathbb{Z}$  · z/2)  $\equiv$  (  $\mathbb{R}$ p. $\wedge$ -cong refl 2z/2 $\equiv$ z )
  x ^ z ■
```

```
help1 : (x :  $\mathbb{R}$ ) .{ q : NonZero x } → (z :  $\mathbb{Z}$ ) → (w :  $\mathbb{Z}\mathbb{C}$ ) → let
  r =  $\mathbb{R}$ p.xz-nonZero { q } {z}
  in ((x ^ z) ^ w) { r }  $\equiv$  x ^ (proj1 (f $\mathbb{Z}$  z) · w)
help1 x z [ v , p ] rewrite help-kz z v p with par v  $\oplus$  p
... | zero rewrite  $\mathbb{Z}$ p.+identityr v |  $\mathbb{F}_2$ p. $\wedge$ -zeror (par z)
  |  $\mathbb{Z}$ p.+identityr (z · v) = cong ( $\_ \cdot$  1 $\mathbb{R}$ ) $  $\mathbb{R}$ p.double-exp x z v
... | one with even-or-odd z
... | even q rewrite  $\mathbb{Z}$ p.+identityr (z · v) | help0 x q
  |  $\mathbb{R}$ p.*-identityr (x ^ z) |  $\mathbb{R}$ p.*-identityr (x ^ (z · v))
  |  $\mathbb{R}$ p.double-exp x z (v - 1 $\mathbb{Z}$ ) = trans (sym $  $\mathbb{R}$ p.sum-exp x (z · (v - 1 $\mathbb{Z}$ )) z)
  $  $\mathbb{R}$ p. $\wedge$ -cong refl $ begin
    z · (v - 1 $\mathbb{Z}$ ) + z  $\equiv$  ( (cong ( $\_ +$  z) $  $\mathbb{Z}$ p.*-distribl-+ z v (- 1 $\mathbb{Z}$ )) )
    z · v + (z · - 1 $\mathbb{Z}$ ) + z  $\equiv$  ( (cong ( $\lambda$  y → z · v + y + z) $  $\mathbb{Z}$ p.*-comm z (- 1 $\mathbb{Z}$ )) )
    z · v + (- 1 $\mathbb{Z}$  · z) + z  $\equiv$  ( (cong ( $\lambda$  y → z · v + y + z) $  $\mathbb{Z}$ p.-1*n $\equiv$ -n z) )
    z · v - z + z  $\equiv$  (  $\mathbb{Z}$ p.+assoc (z · v) (- z) z )
    z · v + (- z + z)  $\equiv$  ( (cong ( $\_ +$  (z · v)) $  $\mathbb{Z}$ p.+inversel z) )
    z · v + 0 $\mathbb{Z}$   $\equiv$  (  $\mathbb{Z}$ p.+identityr (z · v) )
    z · v ■
... | odd q with pred-odd q
... | r rewrite  $\mathbb{R}$ p.*-identityr | x ^ z | |  $\mathbb{R}$ p.*-identityr | x | = begin
  ((x ^ z) ^ (v - 1 $\mathbb{Z}$ )) { _ } · | x ^ z |
   $\equiv$  ( cong2  $\_ \_$  ( $\mathbb{R}$ p.double-exp x z (v - 1 $\mathbb{Z}$ )) helper1 )
  x ^ (z · (v - 1 $\mathbb{Z}$ )) · (x ^ z' · | x |)
   $\equiv$  (  $\mathbb{R}$ p.*-assoc (x ^ (z · (v - 1 $\mathbb{Z}$ ))) (x ^ z') | x | )
  (x ^ (z · (v - 1 $\mathbb{Z}$ )) · x ^ z') · | x |
   $\equiv$  ( (cong ( $\_ \cdot$  | x |) $  $\mathbb{R}$ p.sum-exp x (z · (v - 1 $\mathbb{Z}$ )) z') )
  x ^ (z · (v - 1 $\mathbb{Z}$ ) + z') · | x |
```

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```

≡⟨ (cong (· | x |) $ Rp.^-cong {x} refl helper₂) ⟩
x ^ (z · v - 1ℤ) · | x | ■
where
z' = -1ℤ + z
helper₁ : | x ^ z | ≡ x ^ z' · | x |
helper₁ = begin
| x ^ z |
≡⟨ (cong |·| $ Rp.^-cong {x} refl $ Zp.+identity' z) ⟩
| x ^ (0ℤ + z) |
≡⟨ (cong |·| $ Rp.^-cong {x} refl $ cong (+ z) $ Zp.+inverse' 1ℤ) ⟩
| x ^ (1ℤ - 1ℤ + z) |
≡⟨ (cong |·| $ Rp.^-cong {x} refl $ Zp.+assoc 1ℤ -1ℤ z) ⟩
| x ^ (1ℤ + (-1ℤ + z)) |
≡⟨ (cong |·| $ Rp.sum-exp x 1ℤ (-1ℤ + z)) ⟩
| x ^ 1ℤ · x ^ z' |
≡⟨ (cong (λ y → | y · x ^ z' |) $ Rp.*-identity' x) ⟩
| x · x ^ z' | ≡⟨ Rp.|x||y| x (x ^ z') ⟩
| x | · | x ^ z' | ≡⟨ (cong (· | x |) $ help₀ x r) ⟩
| x | · x ^ z' ≡⟨ Rp.*-comm | x | (x ^ z') ⟩
x ^ z' · | x | ■
helper₂ : z · (v - 1ℤ) + z' ≡ z · v - 1ℤ
helper₂ = begin
z · (v - 1ℤ) + z' ≡⟨ (cong (+ z') $ Zp.*-distrib'++ z v -1ℤ) ⟩
z · v + (z · -1ℤ) + z' ≡⟨ (cong (λ y → z · v + y + z') $ Zp.*-comm z -1ℤ) ⟩
z · v + (-1ℤ · z) + z' ≡⟨ (cong (λ y → z · v + y + z') $ Zp.-1*n≡-n z) ⟩
z · v - z + (-1ℤ + z) ≡⟨ (cong (+_) ((z · v) - z)) $ Zp.+comm -1ℤ z) ⟩
z · v - z + (z - 1ℤ) ≡⟨ Zp.+assoc (z · v) (- z) (z - 1ℤ) ⟩
z · v + (- z + (z - 1ℤ)) ≡⟨ (cong (+_) (z · v)) $ Zp.+assoc (- z) z -1ℤ) ⟩
z · v + ((- z + z) - 1ℤ) ≡⟨ (cong (λ y → z · v + (y - 1ℤ)) $ Zp.+inverse' z) ⟩
z · v + (0ℤ - 1ℤ) ≡⟨ (cong (+_) (z · v)) $ Zp.+identity' -1ℤ) ⟩
z · v - 1ℤ ■

help-par-℔₂-to-ℤ : (x : ℔₂) → par (℔₂-to-ℤ x) ≡ x
help-par-℔₂-to-ℤ x with x
... | zero = refl
... | one = refl
help-par-neg : (x : ℤ) → par (- x) ≡ par x
help-par-neg x with even-or-odd x
... | even p = parity-even $ neg-even p
... | odd p = parity-odd $ neg-odd p
help-p : p ≡ p₁
help-p rewrite th-par-linearity-ℤ {v₁} {- k₁} with par v₁
... | zero rewrite help-par-neg (℔₂-to-ℤ p₁) = help-par-℔₂-to-ℤ p₁
... | one rewrite help-par-neg (℔₂-to-ℤ (¬ p₁)) | help-par-℔₂-to-ℤ (¬ p₁) =
℔₂p.¬-double p₁
help-p₃ : p₃ ≡ p₁₂

```

```
help-p3 = cong (· p2) help-p
```

```
v3+v4≡v12 : v3 + v4 ≡ v12
v3+v4≡v12 with par v1 ⊕ p1
... | zero rewrite Zp.+-identityr v1 = Zp.+-identityr (v1 · v2)
... | one = begin
  (v1 - 1Z) · v2 + 1Z · v2 ≡⟨ Zp.*-distribr v2 (v1 - 1Z) 1Z ⟩
  (v1 - 1Z + 1Z) · v2 ≡⟨ (cong (· v2) $ Zp.+-assoc v1 (- 1Z) 1Z) ⟩
  (v1 + 0Z) · v2 ≡⟨ (cong (· v2) $ Zp.+-identityr v1) ⟩
  v1 · v2 ■
```

```
help-even : Even (k3 + v4 - k12)
help-even = parity-even-1 $ begin
  par ((k3 + v4) - k12) ≡⟨ th-par-linearity-Z {k3 + v4} {- k12} ⟩
  par (k3 + v4) ⊕ par (- k12)
  ≡⟨ cong2 _⊕_ (th-par-linearity-Z {k3} {v4}) (help-par-neg k12) ⟩
  (par k3 ⊕ par v4) ⊕ par k12
  ≡⟨ cong2 (λ a b → (a ⊕ par (v4)) ⊕ b)
    (trans (help-par-F2-to-Z (par v3 ⊕ p3)) (cong (_⊕_ (par v3)) help-p3))
    (help-par-F2-to-Z (par v12 ⊕ p12))) ⟩
  ((par v3 ⊕ p12) ⊕ par v4) ⊕ (par v12 ⊕ p12)
  ≡⟨ cong (_⊕_ (par v12 ⊕ p12)) helper ⟩
  ((par v3 ⊕ par v4) ⊕ p12) ⊕ (par v12 ⊕ p12)
  ≡⟨ (cong (λ x → (x ⊕ p12) ⊕ (par v12 ⊕ p12))) $
    th-par-linearity-Z {v3} {v4}) ⟩
  (par (v3 + v4) ⊕ p12) ⊕ (par v12 ⊕ p12)
  ≡⟨ cong (λ x → (par x ⊕ p12) ⊕ (par v12 ⊕ p12)) v3+v4≡v12 ⟩
  (par v12 ⊕ p12) ⊕ (par v12 ⊕ p12)
  ≡⟨ F2p.⊕-self (par v12 ⊕ p12) ⟩
  zero ■
```

where

```
helper : (par v3 ⊕ p12) ⊕ par v4 ≡ (par v3 ⊕ par v4) ⊕ p12
helper = begin
  (par v3 ⊕ p12) ⊕ par v4 ≡⟨ F2p.⊕-assoc (par v3) p12 (par v4) ⟩
  par v3 ⊕ (p12 ⊕ par v4) ≡⟨ (cong (_⊕_ (par v3)) $ F2p.⊕-comm p12 (par v4)) ⟩
  par v3 ⊕ (par v4 ⊕ p12) ≡⟨ F2p.⊕-assoc (par v3) (par v4) p12 ⟩
  (par v3 ⊕ par v4) ⊕ p12 ■
```

```
help2 : | x | ^ (k3 + v4 - k12) ≡ x ^ (k3 + v4 - k12)
help2 with half-even help-even
... | z/2 , 2z/2≡z = begin
  | x | ^ (k3 + v4 - k12) ≡⟨ Rp.^-cong refl 2z/2≡z ⟩
  | x | ^ (2Z · z/2) ≡⟨ Rp.|x|^2z x z/2 ⟩
  x ^ (2Z · z/2) ≡⟨ Rp.^-cong refl 2z/2≡z ⟩
  x ^ (k3 + v4 - k12) ■
```

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```

help3 : (v3 - k3) + (k3 + v4 - k12) ≡ v12 - k12
help3 rewrite ℤp.+--assoc k3 v4 (- k12) = begin
  (v3 - k3) + (k3 + (v4 - k12)) ≡⟨ ℤp.+--inverse-middlel v3 k3 (v4 - k12) ⟩
  v3 + (v4 - k12)                ≡⟨ ℤp.+--assoc v3 v4 (- k12) ⟩
  (v3 + v4) - k12                ≡⟨ (cong (- k12) v3+v4≡v12) ⟩
  v12 - k12 ■

```

```

help4 : x ^ (v3 - k3) · | x | ^ (k3 + v4) ≡ x ^ (v12 - k12) · | x | ^ k12
help4 rewrite sym $ ℤp.+--identityr (k3 + v4) | sym $ ℤp.+--inversel k12
| sym $ ℤp.+--assoc (k3 + v4) (- k12) k12
| ℝp.sum-exp | x | ((k3 + v4) - k12) k12 | help2
| sym $ ℝp.*--assoc (x ^ (v3 - k3)) (x ^ (k3 + v4 - k12)) (| x | ^ k12)
= cong (- · | x | ^ k12) $ begin
  x ^ (v3 - k3) · x ^ (k3 + v4 - k12)
  ≡⟨ ℝp.sum-exp x (v3 - k3) (k3 + v4 - k12) ⟩
  x ^ ((v3 - k3) + (k3 + v4 - k12))
  ≡⟨ (cong (λ e → x ^ e) $ help3) ⟩
  x ^ (v12 - k12) ■

```

□

Remark (Absolute value). As defined in section 1.4, a real elevated to the power of the even unit is its absolute value: $x^l = |x|$.

Proof.

```

xl : (x : ℝ) .{ _ : NonZero x } → x ^ 1 ≡ | x |
xl x rewrite ℝp.*--identityr | x | = ℝp.*--identityl | x |

```

□

Remark (Sign function). A real number elevated to the power of the odd zero is the sign function: $x^o = \text{sgn}(x)$.

Proof.

```

xo : (x : ℝ) .{ _ : NonZero x } → x ^ 0 ≡ sgn x
xo x { p } rewrite ℝp.-1-distrib-* x 1ℝ { p } { 1-nonZero } | ℝp.1-1
| ℝp.*--identityr (x-1) | ℝp.*--identityr | x | with ℝp.≤-total x 0ℝ
... | inj1 x ≤ 0 = trans (sym $ ℝp.~distrib'-* (x-1) x)
                        (cong (-_) $ ℝp.*--inversel x)
... | inj2 x ≥ 0 = ℝp.*--inversel x

```

□

Future work

Agda implementation

For what concerns the Agda implementation of the proofs it would be interesting to remove all the postulates in `PostulatedReals.agda` defining a type for real numbers in a constructive way. I already started this (`R.agda`) following [Bish67], but I had to stop due to the fact that it was taking a lot of time only to define the basic operations (addition and multiplication).

Then another improvement which could be done is to replace, in the definition of real exponentiation to integers and its properties, the witnesses of the base being different from zero, with witnesses of the base being non null or the exponent be positive. In fact with the actual certificate of the base being non zero we are not permitted to compute and prove for 0^z , whit z positive.

Functions by cases in a polynomial-like form

The last remark tell us that using complete integers as exponents we can write functions with a discontinuity in zero. We can use this fact to define an extension of polynomials, which have complete integer exponents. With those “polynomials” we could write all functions which are interpolable with a polynomial for $x \leq 0$ and with another for $x \geq 0$.

We can further extend this concept summing some of those extended “polynomials”, translated on the x axis (evaluated in $x - \bar{x}$): every of those “polynomials” has a different discontinuity point \bar{x} . So those hyper “polynomials” could represent all functions by cases for which each case can be represented with a polynomial.

For example $\frac{(x-a)^o - (x-b)^o}{2}$ is always zero, except in the interval (a, b) , and so can be used as a “mask” for that case.

Complete rationals

As we have defined the commutative ring $\mathbb{Z}_C = \mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{F}_2$, we can define also a commutative ring over $\mathbb{Q}_H = \mathbb{Q} \times \mathbb{F}_2$. In this case however we cannot prove $\mathbb{Q} \subset \mathbb{Q}_H$. Defining $\mathbb{Q}_{\bar{H}} = \left\{ \frac{q}{i} : q \in \mathbb{Q}_H \right\}$ and $\mathbb{Q}_C = \mathbb{Q}_H \sqcup \mathbb{Q}_{\bar{H}}$ we could prove:

1. $\mathbb{Q} \subset \mathbb{Q}_C$;
2. The division of two complete integers is in \mathbb{Q}_C ;
3. $\mathbb{Q}_C = \{x/y : x, y \in \mathbb{Z}_C; y \neq 0\}$.

References

- [Bish67] BISHOP, ERRETT: *Foundations of Constructive Analysis*: New York, NY, USA: Mcgraw-Hill, 1967